

**LIVED EXPERIENCES OF FORMER PERSONS DEPRIVED OF LIBERTY ON THE
WELFARE AND DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM:
SOCIAL REINTEGRATION CONTEXT**

Romeo G. Sarenas, Christian M. Serabia, Rod Ardery D. Culaban,
Angel C. Camitoc, Julius N. Cagara, Vincent E. Pagunsan,
John Clark M. Mesias, LPT, MPE

College of Criminology, Burauen Community College, Burauen, Leyte, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12497533>

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to explore the experiences of former persons deprived of liberty (PDLs) with the Welfare and Development Programs (WDP) administered by the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP), focusing on their social reintegration. Using a phenomenological approach, it addressed how BJMP's WDP facilitated reintegration, the application of training in various life domains by former PDLs, and their recommendations for BJMP. Ten former PDLs from Burauen District Jail participated as co-researchers, achieving data saturation by the fifth interview. Data were collected through narrative accounts and responses, validated via verbatim transcription and member checking. Aged 40-50, the co-researchers provided insights into themes such as Effective Program Provision, Self-Reflection, Easier Job Placement, and Program Continuation, with sub-themes highlighting positive outcomes, interpersonal skills, life skills, and application of learned skills. Participants stressed the role of BJMP's programs in attitude change, skill development, and societal reintegration, benefiting their employability, relationships, and overall rehabilitation. The study concluded that BJMP's WDP significantly supports successful social reintegration, recommending program continuity, enhancement, collaboration with agencies like TESDA, and strengthened partnerships with governmental and non-governmental organizations to ensure effective implementation. It highlighted the necessity of comprehensive rehabilitation efforts for former PDLs, crucial for their societal reentry and the reduction of recidivism.

Keywords: *Lived Experiences, Welfare and Development, Social Reintegration, Former Persons Deprived of Liberty*

INTRODUCTION

One of the critical factors in the success of rehabilitation programs is the offender's adherence to the program's guidelines and their willingness to make meaningful changes in their lives. Most offenders tend to believe that rules do not apply to them, which contributes to their imprisonment (DeLong and Reichert, 2019). This phenomenon in the contemporary period aligns with the principle of consequentialism, which focuses on managing and treating prisoners to prepare them for a productive life post-imprisonment (Bulow, 2014).

Globally, government and security agencies have institutionalized programs aimed at reforming the psycho-behavioral aspects of offenders (Larsen, 2019). Manka et al. (2021) proposed several interventions representing a small sample of the many initiatives supported by the court system, often in partnership with local agencies and organizations. Some programs specifically target particular offender groups, such as former PDLs and high-risk young former PDLs. Despite the varying criminological semantics, individuals under penal facilities undergo personal reformation.

Solely, rehabilitation programs have continued in some areas with modifications. In Estonia, one-on-one sessions have persisted; in Thailand, preventive measures such as allowing trained detainees and prison officials to lead basic vocational training and ensuring adequate training materials have enabled the continuation of work programs. Online solutions were implemented where digital technology was available, facilitating the adaptation or introduction of new programs. For instance, in Ireland's Mountjoy Jail, online access to university courses was provided, and universities in the United States continued or initiated new courses for incarcerated individuals via online platforms (Global Prison Trends, 2021).

In addition, various jails and prisons offer diverse rehabilitation programs, including educational initiatives, recreational activities, and livelihood programs. One key area of focus is life skill training, which inmates frequently access. These programs, often referred to as counseling interventions, operate on the premise that many offenders may lack the basic understanding necessary to function effectively in society upon their release. Consequently, these courses cover a range of essential skills such as job application and interview techniques, financial and household management, healthy living practices, and parenting skills.

More so, rehabilitation programs, encompassing educational, vocational, and counseling initiatives, are critical in assisting former persons deprived of liberty (PDLs) in abandoning criminal lifestyles (Reamico, 2022). In Ghana, the prison system emphasizes the importance of providing inmates with basic and vocational education, aiming to reduce unemployment and facilitate social integration post-release (Baffour, 2021).

Hence, the Philippine Corrections System, comprised of government-run facilities, community volunteers, and private enterprises, is responsible for the incarceration, punishment, and rehabilitation of convicted individuals. The Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) was established to address challenges in jail

management and criminology. Under R.A. 6975, the BJMP holds operational and administrative responsibility over all municipal, district, and city jails.

As part of its mandate, the BJMP envisions itself as a dynamic institution dedicated to the humane safekeeping and development of inmates (Section 2, BJMP Manual 2015). In 2010, the BJMP released a policy regarding the implementation of the Therapeutic Community and Modality Program (TCMP), which serves as a model for the PDLs Welfare and Development Program. The Therapeutic Community, as defined by the Philippine Department of Justice, is an environment that facilitates mutual help among inmates.

Despite receiving rehabilitation and learning skills through BJMP's livelihood programs, many released PDLs struggle to apply these skills outside prison due to societal mistrust and lack of opportunities. Djoana and Aoas (2020) noted that these livelihood programs aim to instill hope in prisoners rather than reinforce the perception that they have no future.

This study examines the socio-economic impact of BJMP's livelihood programs and the social lives of former PDLs. By engaging directly with former offenders and understanding their daily experiences, the researcher aims to uncover their urgent needs, the socio-economic effects of the BJMP programs, and the challenges they face in reintegration. This approach will enable the formulation of practical recommendations benefiting both former PDLs and society at large.

Lastly, the study aspires to significantly impact the lives of former PDLs by guiding them toward a positive future. By providing insights into the outcomes of welfare and development programs, this research will be invaluable to BJMP staff and other concerned organizations, offering crucial information to enhance the support provided to former PDLs.

Research Questions

The study focused on the assessment of the Former Persons Deprived of Liberty towards the Welfare and Development Program of the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology in the Social Reintegration Context

Specifically, it intends to explore on the following;

1. How does the Welfare and Development Program of the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology facilitate the reintegration of former persons deprived of liberty?
2. How do former persons deprived of liberty apply the training received under the Welfare and Development of Program of the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology across education, recreation, spirituality and livelihood in the course of reintegration?
3. What are the recommendations of former persons deprived of liberty towards the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To assess the welfare and development programs for former persons deprived of liberty in Burauen District Jail, this study employed a qualitative research design to explain life events and give them significance.

This qualitative phenomenological study documented the experiences of former inmates and how the Welfare and Development Programs (WDP) of the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) assisted them in the context of social reintegration. The purpose of the study was to assess the WDP-BJMP programs provided by the Burauen District Jail. In this context, the researcher followed the guidance of Creswell (2013), utilizing qualitative research methods, particularly through the phenomenological approach.

Research Participants

The study's participants were former persons deprived of liberty (PDLs) from Burauen District Jail. The participants were purposively selected to ensure that the data collected would sufficiently address the study's main question. According to documents provided by the district jail, ten former PDLs who had served their sentences for the same violation (R.A. 9165) were included in the study.

To assess the program offered by Burauen District Jail, the researchers specifically chose these former PDLs because they could share their experiences related to the implemented welfare and development program. Their insights were crucial for identifying fundamental ways to improve the program.

Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling was used in this study. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling method based on selected characteristics of a population and the study's objective. It is also known as selective, judgmental, or subjective sampling. Hence, this method is frequently used and well-regarded in qualitative research for selecting information-rich data relevant to the phenomenon of interest. Purposive sampling was also used in this study because the process of choosing participants was based on the programs being studied rather than merely explaining them (Campbell et al., 2020).

The inclusion criteria for choosing the research participants were: a) released PDLs of the year 2018, b) residing in Julita, Tabon, Dagami, and Burauen Leyte, and c) released PDLs in 2018 with the same violation (R.A. 9165). The researcher used pseudonyms to ensure the anonymity of the participants, thus upholding their identities.

Research Locale

This study was conducted among former persons deprived of liberty at the Burauen District Jail, located in the 2nd District of Leyte Province.

2009

For accessibility and its status as a Red Orchid Awardee, the study chose Burauen District Jail for its implementation of the Welfare and Development Program. The researcher selected Leyte Province, specifically the 2nd District or Burauen District Jail, as the site of the study.

Research Instruments

The primary instrument for data collection was a semi-structured interview guide that underwent pilot testing and credibility checks. The focus of the interview guide was to assess the programs offered by Burauen District Jail to former persons deprived of liberty. It consisted of open-ended questions derived from the study's problem statement. During the interviews, additional probing questions were posed based on participants' responses. The researcher employed indirect questioning techniques to elicit participants' explanations and perspectives on the implemented Welfare and Development Program of BJMP, covering areas such as Education, Livelihood, Spirituality, and Recreation.

More so, writing implements and materials were used to record participants' responses, while audio recording was conducted simultaneously, as agreed upon with the participants beforehand.

Data Analysis

In this study, the Colaizzi Method was employed to conduct Inductive Thematic Analysis of participants' narrative accounts. The primary goal was to use Colaizzi's descriptive phenomenological approach to describe and illustrate the participants' experiences, while identifying emerging themes and exploring their interconnected relationships (Wirihana, 2018).

Ensuring the trustworthiness of the qualitative research, as emphasized by Stahl and King (2020), involved meticulous attention to data collection and analysis. The data underwent rigorous evaluation against criteria including credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Nowel et al., 2019). An interview schedule was utilized for direct data gathering from participants. The data analysis process was guided step-by-step by qualitative research experts: each participant's transcript was thoroughly reviewed and cross-checked to capture the breadth of experiences related to the Welfare and Development Program administered by the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology at Burauen District Jail.

Further, significant statements were meticulously extracted, transcribed with detailed references for verification, and organized into meaningful sub-themes. These sub-themes were then synthesized into overarching themes that formed the basis of a comprehensive description supported by relevant literature. Thus, the study culminated in outlining the fundamental structure of the phenomenon under investigation, and so, the researchers sought validation of their findings from the participants to ensure alignment between the descriptive results and the lived experiences of former persons deprived of liberty who were released in 2018 with similar violations.

Ethical Considerations

In conducting the research, several ethical considerations were addressed. Permission was obtained from relevant authorities to conduct interviews, and great care was taken to protect participants' rights and ensure confidentiality of collected data. Participants were given the option to choose a convenient time and location for interviews.

Hence, the participants were also informed about the researcher's journal, which documented perspectives, rationales, insights, and biases throughout the study process. Participants were assured of their right to withhold or withdraw information as desired, with a commitment to maintain confidentiality by ensuring that their identities would not be disclosed in any public reports or shared with others. Researchers ensured flexibility in scheduling interviews based on participants' availability and preferences for answering prepared questions.

All study-related costs were covered by the researchers as part of their academic responsibilities. During face-to-face interviews, strict adherence to safety measures, including wearing face masks, was observed. Participants did not receive financial compensation but were acknowledged with a small token of appreciation for their valuable time and contribution. Finally, after completing all study procedures, researchers planned to provide participants with a clear explanation of the study's findings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the narrative accounts derived from the collected data, encompassing themes and sub-themes that emerged from participants' responses. The primary objective of this study was to vividly capture the lived experiences of former persons deprived of liberty regarding the welfare and development programs, as well as their experiences with social integration.

Employing a phenomenological research design, the study aimed to address the following research questions:

1. How did the Welfare and Development Program of the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology facilitate the reintegration of former persons deprived of liberty?
2. How did former persons deprived of liberty apply the training received under the Welfare and Development Program of the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology across education, recreation, spirituality, and livelihood during their reintegration process?
3. What recommendations did former persons deprived of liberty have for the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology?

The study involved ten pre-identified co-researchers who were former persons deprived of liberty from Burauen District Jail. Data saturation was achieved by the fifth

interview. The analysis relied on narrative accounts and responses provided by these five co-researchers.

To ensure the validity of the findings, verbatim transcriptions of narrative accounts were returned to the co-researchers for member checking, validating the accuracy and authenticity of the information they provided. Results were presented with identifiers as FPDL (1) to (5), italicized, with translations enclosed in parentheses where necessary, accompanied by quoted responses and researcher feedback as supporting evidence.

The study participants comprised five former persons deprived of liberty who were released from Burauen District Jail. The profile of the co-researchers is summarized in Table No. 1 below:

Table 1 Age and Place of Origin of the Participants

Participants	Characteristics	
	Age	Place of Origin
FPDL 1	42	Julita, Leyte
FPDL 2	45	Burauen, Leyte
FPDL 3	47	Julita, Leyte
FPDL 4	50	Burauen, Leyte
FPDL 5	48	Burauen, Leyte

The table above illustrates that all participants fall within the age bracket of 40-50 years old. This demographic suggests that these individuals still have significant opportunities to lead fulfilling lives by applying the skills and knowledge acquired through programs provided by the agency

Thematic Reflection

The following are the discussions and interpretations of the common themes that emerged from the narratives of the participants.

Theme 1: Provision of Effective Programs

Without sufficient opportunities for skill development and capacity growth, an individual frequently returns to the society that imprisoned him or her as a jaded foe of that civilization. Such a former persons deprived of liberty frequently feels victimized rather than disciplined, which fuels his or her need for retribution. Additionally, former persons deprived of liberty who is viewed as one by society will probably cause more harm than good.

The rehabilitation of prisoners should start the moment they are taken into custody and should last until their release (Igbo, 2007). This is done to make sure they use the skills they learned throughout rehabilitation to lead law-abiding lives in society. Numerous initiatives are in place to steer offenders away from crime and toward worthwhile endeavors that make crime unappealing or detestable, such as moral or religious institutions, education, and vocational training. According to, FPDL 1 he said

that the programs provided for him are helpful in the sense that it changed and prepared for him to go back to the community.

“Naka bulig iton gehap na mga programa. Kay pag hikanhi ha community amo na ito nag bag’o ako”. [The program was helpful, since, when referred to the community, that’s it, I’ve changed].

On a similar note, FPDL 2 stated that the program helped him to overcome his longingness to his family while he was in jail.

“Oo naman, an programa an nakabulig ha ak para baga deri dumuro nak kamingaw nak pamilya”. [Yes it is, the program help me to ease the feeling of missing my].

Meanwhile, FPDL 3 said that he made use of the programs as his leeway in entertainment while at the prison.

“Oo gad, saypa kay amo iton an akon baga nagiging kali-awan”. [Probably yes, most especially that this serves as my pleasure].

The responses of the participants concurred to the study of (Uche et al., 2015) as it talks about former persons deprived of liberty who actively pursue rehabilitation while they are in the custody of the jail agency as they develop skills that will help them find resources, opportunities, and employment once they are released (Uche et al., 2015). In collaboration with the government, the jail administration has offered a variety of rehabilitation programs in a number of institutions. These programs include a variety of topics, including farming, adult literacy, tailoring, welding, and woodworking.

These results are in line with Inciardi's (2009) observation that welfare and development programs involve a variety of activities, all of which can have an effect on prisoners' rehabilitation and effective reintegration into society after release, either directly or indirectly.

Sub-theme 1.1 Positive Outcomes of Program

After the persons deprived of liberty have served their sentences is always a major concern for both the government and society. This, however, can only be secured by providing them with a respectful opportunity to earn a living (Djoana and Aoas, 2020). Livelihood programs perse aim to alter attitudes, knowledge, and skills through a program of action service and education

However, this rehabilitation is a serious priority for both the government and society after they have fulfilled their terms. This, however, can only be achieved by providing them with a respectable means of earning a living. According to FPDL 1, he said that these programs are helpful for them so that they will not be bored during their stay inside.

“Usa ito hiya nga programa na inayad para haamon nga nadidto, para baga diri gehap kami ma lontogan pag inukoy didto”. [That is a program made for us that was in Jail, and to ease our boredom in our stay in the Jail].

Meanwhile, FPDL 3 said that these programs are helpful for him because it was his avenue not to commit the mistake again.

“Para ha akon, koan iton hiya, ini nga mga borohaton nga igo buligan inin aton mga PDL na diri na makasala otro”. [For me, these programs are helpful in terms of PDL because it helped th PDL not to commit the mistake again].

More so, FPDL 4 gave emphasis that the programs have played an important role to him.

“Oo naka experience gadman ak ton didto, saypa kay baga nakabulig iton haak”. [Yes, I've experience it in the Jail, most especially that it helps me].

With the passage of time, the responses of the participants agreed on the study of (Cano et al., 2023) that livelihood programs assist former persons deprived of liberty in building new abilities that can be utilized to earn money both inside and outside of jail.

With the premise of the BJMP's livelihood programs. It is still too early to tell how the program improves people's lives of former detainees, and what influence the program had on the participants' lives.

Sub-theme 1.2 Interpersonal Skills

Giving and receiving social assistance is a vital aspect of both individuals' and communities' existence. Such assistance is frequently exchanged within families, learning and working environments, communities, among coworkers, and in other connections (Education Reimagined, 2023).

And thus, policymakers thought that former prisoners needed help and support from family, relatives, and friends, as well as institutional institutions such as criminal justice agencies, correctional facilities, prison officers, and social welfare programs. In fact, FPDL1 described on his experiences on the importance of recreational activities.

“an recreation, orog man ton didto basketball, education liwat, mga pan ngiskwela sugad han ALS, pero an akon gud baga naka experience is an spirituality, kay baga sigi man gud nak ampo ton didto na makagawas na”. [The recreation, which is more on basketball, on the other hand, in Education was more on schooling just like with ALS, but what I experience the most is the spirituality. Since, I was more on doing prayers in there in able to get out].

While FPDL2 also gave emphasis on his experiences on the recreational activities that the BJMP provided for them as it develops his camaraderie among mates.

“Hito nga Recreation luwat, ini nga butang an akon paborito. Ha sulod han presuhan damo an mga pamulay nga nadidto ngan binuligan nakon para deri ako luntugon sugad, basketball, volleyball, table tennis ngan chess. Ini nga mga aktibidad it pinaka rason hito nga maupay nga relasyon ngan hit pagka murulay ha ika preso”. [In the area of Recreation, this area of the program was

my favorite. Inside the Jail there were many sports that was available that I have participated to kill my boredom namely, basketball, volleyball, table tennis and chess. These activities are the main reason in the creation of harmonious relationship and sportsmanship towards co-pdl].

On the same note, FPD6 enjoyed the recreational opportunity that was given to while on the custody of the BJMP.

“ha sulod han presuhan, mayda mga sports nga gin hatag para mag muruglay ngan mag upay an lawas luwat. Damoay adto nga sports mayda, basketball, volleyball, table tennis, ngan chess ngan basketball nak pinaka paborito kay katungod na baga player man ak anay ugsa ak ma sentensiyahan. Usa pa, namulay akon basketball hit mga competition sugad barangay ngan munusipyo nga lebel yana nga adi na ako ha hit kumyunidad”. [Inside the Jail, they were provided sports to play and to stay physically fit. There were numerous sports to play namely, basketball, volleyball, table tennis and chess and that basketball is my favorite one since I was some kind of a player before I served my sentence. Additionally, I play basketball during competitions such as barangay and municipal level now that I am in the community].

On a regular basis, correctional officers contact with these persons deprived of liberty, are a part of this interpersonal interaction. Interpersonal communication are truly abilities that are frequently underestimated. Simply said, it's necessary to place more emphasis on recreational activities that paves a way of an effective communication skills in corrections training. Knowing how to communicate and listen to others can help prevent incidents involving the use of force with offenders.

Sub-theme 1.3 Life Key Skills

For many people who have been deprived of their liberty likewise leaving jail and reentering society can be a tough process. Many people who have been deprived of their liberty are well-equipped to conduct productive lives once they are released. Various programs and organizations focus on teaching people who have been deprived of their liberty life skills. Hence, being a part of one of these programs is useful as it educates persons deprived of liberty a wide range of skills in order to aid their eventual reintegration into society.

Prison administrations provide persons deprived of liberty with external certification for their practical training, with documents that do not indicate that the skills were learned in prison, allowing for a smooth transition of former persons deprived of liberty to freedom (Ortaleza and Nabe, 2020). According to FPD1 said that he has learned a lot on the livelihood program.

“May ada ada kogad nahabaruan parti hito nga programa. Kay ha livelihood dako adto nak nahabaruan”. [I was able to learn something within that program, however, it was on the livelihood, I've learned a lot].

On the same note, FPD3 shared something on what he have learned on the education and livelihood.

“Sugad han education, baga na update ini an akon mga nahibaruan. Han livelihood liwat, nanhibaro ako pag ayad hini nga mga magkote”. [In terms of Education, it updated my previous knowledge. With livelihood, I was able to learn meticulous task].

While FPD5 have shared his learnings in general.

“Oo, baga damo iton akon mga nahibaruan didto parti hito nga programa”. [Yes, I’ve acquire several learnings in the Jail relative to that program]

Participants' responses agreed with Samilo et al., (2020), who stated in their paper that BJMP Valenzuela also works on and the strengths and weaknesses of the program to reform people and provide persons deprived of liberty (PDLs) with skills and learning that will be useful for them.

Former persons deprived of livert may also learn essential employability skills through these programs, which may lead to opportunities for employment upon their release to support themselves and even their families and live a reformed life that is different from their one before entering jail.

Theme 2 Self-Reflection

This training, which will be prioritized for prisoners with low levels of education and no prior work experience, is intended to improve their chances of successful self-employment after release. Simultaneously, the initiative is a first step toward the construction of a silver jewelry manufacturing and marketing facility, which will employ offenders and generate cash for them.

Understanding former persons deprived of liberty reentry into society after release is required for knowledge of their desistance processes (Vivares, 2023). As well as jails with a nice and well-organized social climate that is safe, helpful, and well-policed likewise treated convicts with humanity has to be detailed. According to FPD1, he have learned on how to use the rosary and used it as his weapon on his fight while he was in jail.

“Amo iton an parti han kanan spirituality, sugad han mga pan rosary ngan pan ngadi, kay baga amo man gud iton an akon masyado nga nagagamit”. [That’s it, regarding spirituality, like those with rosaries, and with prayers, since that was mostly what I can used].

Meanwhile, FPD2 have also explored on his ways on how he can supasds the problem through reading and other legal advices.

“Mayda gad gehap, amo naton han ak pagbinasa parte han akon kaso, nga kon paano ak makalosot, parte na gehap ito hit education”. [I also have those learnings, and that was in relation to my reading habits regarding my case, on how would I be dismissed, and that is already concomitant to education].

On the same manner, FPD5 have gained learning that are useful on his present time as former person deprived of liberty.

“Sugad han kanan Edukasyon, mayda ko nabaruan ngadto kay tinutduan man ak nira, ngan hit livelihood, nabaro ak mag ayad Parol nga akon binaligya kada ma pasko, nabaro ako mangadi ngan magka maya koneksyon haiya, ngan nakabulig luwat adto pag upay pa nak mulay han basketball “. [Like the area of Education, I learned something for they were teaching me inside the Jail, and for the Livelihood, I learned to make a Parol that I sell during Christmas vacation, I learned to pray and to connect with him, and It have helped me improve my skills in basketball].

When former persons deprived of liberty are released from prison, they typically learn that their hopes for resuming normal life are not easy. This is especially true for long-term persons deprived of liberty who are less likely to meet various learning that are required in the social reintegration context.

Sub-theme Application of Learned Skills

Former persons deprived of liberty who developed good soft skills in prison have a better chance of decreasing their term, re-entering successfully, and finding meaningful work ((Cano et al., 2023)). As a result, an effective soft skills program necessitates careful skill selection and concentration, adaptive resources, various teaching techniques, continuous assessment, and precise tailored feedback and encouragement.

Thus, former persons deprived of liberty can extend soft skills training outside the correctional setting. According to FPDL2 shared his experiences relative to the phenomenon.

“kay an ak gin pagtoto-unan nak pansin is an ak kaso, naha apply ko logod an ak mga nabaruan parti nak kaso didto nga diri dapat buhaton dinhi, mga panotdo dinhi”. [What I was focusing was my case, but I were able to apply my learning relative to my studies of my case, lectures from the jail].

Same sentiment was shared by FPDL3 have applied his learnings on applying for a job that he was not able to encounter any difficulty.

“An akon baga mga nahabaruan tikang ha Jail, baga waray koman problema han akon pag apply hadto dinhi” [With all the learnings that I acquired from the Jail, it seems that I did not face problems with its application here in the community].

While FDL5 gave an emphasis on the usage of the learnings from the program that he can use in the social reintegration context.

“Oo, naha anu ko tun nga ak nabaruan about han livelihood, kay makakabulig gud ito haimo kun ada kana ha kumyunidad “. [Yes, I have applied those skills that I have acquired but, in the livelihood, I am satisfied about it since the course that has been offered can be used in a sustainable career once you are out in the community].

Former persons deprived of liberty can, in fact, use their acquired abilities in a variety of ways after their release. They can put their skills to use by looking for work or starting their own business. Teaching prisoner with practical work skills can boost their employability and provide them with better job opportunities, or better entrepreneurial abilities to assist them in self-employment.

Theme 3 Finding a Job Easier

The major objective of correctional officers is to instruct and teach former people who have been deprived of their freedom a variety of valuable occupations and assist them enhance their self-esteem, decision-making skills, and confidence in their future. Importantly, these professions will improve their employability, provide better employment opportunities, or, in the case of self-employment, better entrepreneurial skills to support them.

According to an Urban Institute study of Baltimore-area on former persons deprived of liberty, on social reintegration context tend to come from a concentrated collection of communities with "above-average unemployment rates. According to FPDL2 he has not encountered any problem during his application instead he was given advices.

“Dinhi ha community, baga waray man ako ig agi hin problema han pag apply hini nga akon nga nahibaroan, bagat, nanhihingarayag pa an tawo nga nasusumatan nga amo ini, na ayaw diri dapat ta iton buhaton, delikado”. [Here in the community, I did not face problems in terms of applying these learnings that I acquired. Most of the citizen was even happy that I was able to share or impart my knowledge unto them, that they shouldn't do this because it's dangerous].

While FPDL4 shared also the same sentiment that he had not encounter any difficulty while he was applying for a job.

“Han pamiling han trabaho, kinaluyan ako han Ginoo nga waray ako kurian og waray magka problema han pag apply hin trabaho”. [Upon looking for a Job, I am blessed that I didn't have the difficulty or an issue in applying for a work].

On the same manner, FPDL5 have also shared his experiences that the prison have taught him so many lessons and those were very useful.

“An ak mga nabaruan didto sulod han presuhan, dako an gamit ha ak”. [The skills I have acquired inside the Jail was beneficial to me. And luckily upon looking for a job I didn't find any difficulty to be hired because of my past record].

These comments contradict the findings of Visher et al. (2011), who found that a high majority of former offenders have poor levels of educational attainment and work experience, health issues, and other personal qualities that make them difficult to hire.

For many of the participant's, finding work was a significant goal. As they were being released, their employment is a crucial component of the procedure for re-

entry jobs, more than just a consistent source of cash, can offer former inmates with a feeling of structure and responsibility as they try to reintegrate following release. Fortunately, in the context of Bureau District Jail, former persons deprived of liberty did not face a difficult path to finding and keeping work.

Theme 4 Continuation of the Programs

Prisons and jails are institutions for penal reform and rehabilitation. Correctional institutions likewise are supervised by the Department of Justice's Bureau of Corrections. They serve as a safe haven for education, socialization, moral healing, and self-improvement. The Bureau of Jail Management and Penology, specifically, is part of the Department of the Interior and Local Government, which in general oversees district, city, and municipal jails.

Livelihood services embraced the productivity of viable livelihood initiatives by reducing costs, looking for better markets, producing more, and improving quality (Patlunag, 2020). Included in the educational services are the facilitation of continued education for prisoners as well as the education of young and illiterate inmates. That is FPDL1 appeal from the department to continuously hold th program as it is helpful on the context of social reintegration.

“Angay ton paupayon kay maupay man an amon pan gawas nganhi, maupay man an palakad, kutob yana waray man kami ton manmalik ngadto ha presohan, бага nag bag’o na”. [It should be improved since our released here was with a good process, until this day, we did not return to the Jail, cause, of real reformation].

While FPDL3 shared the same vision for the programs that BJMP ahs provided.

“Amo ito, kon makusog man ito yana, pakosgon pa ito nira, para man liwat hit kaupayan hit PDL”.[That’s it, if it was currently strong, then make it even stronger, well, that’s for the welfare of the PDL].

The delivery of various services can be measured by gauging former persons deprived of liberty's satisfaction with their quality of life. The degree of life that adds to happiness, contentment, and mental health advantages is referred to as the quality of life. Understanding their quality of life is essential for informing the government, jail administrators, and the community about the inmates' current situation. Measuring their level of happiness with their quality of life could provide a foundation for developing and designing effective and efficient rehabilitation programs (Patlunag, 2020).

Conclusions

The results of the assessment, derived from the narratives of former persons deprived of liberty, and the qualitative findings disclosed four major themes and seven sub-themes as follows: Theme 1: Provisions of Effective Programs, with sub-themes Positive Outcomes of Programs, Interpersonal Skills, and Life Key Skills. Theme 2: Self-Reflection, with sub-theme Application of Learned Skills. Theme 3: Finding Easier

Jobs. Theme 4: Continuation of the Programs. The results demonstrated that the programs provided by the BJMP-WDP were very useful and significantly aided former persons deprived of liberty in the context of social reintegration, particularly for those who worked to change for the better.

This was congruent with the study by Estillore and Aoas (2020), which found that the BJMP provided livelihood programs focusing on skill-based training for former persons deprived of liberty, as they learned and developed new skills that were extremely valuable. This was vital to their reintegration into normal society. The BJMP's livelihood projects yielded positive results and had a beneficial impact on the lives of former persons deprived of liberty. Furthermore, the employment opportunities available to former persons deprived of liberty improved their socioeconomic standing.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations for improvement and enhancements were provided:

1. The BJMP Burauen District Jail should continue and expand its livelihood programs, as they have made a significant contribution to the lives of former persons deprived of liberty.
 2. The BJMP should offer more livelihood training, such as welding, by strengthening its collaboration with TESDA. T
 3. The BJMP Burauen District Jail should also improve and strengthen its linkages and collaborations with other government and non-government agencies to assist in the efficient implementation of livelihood programs for former persons deprived of liberty. Moreover, enhancing the monitoring and evaluation processes for these programs is essential to ensure their effectiveness and to make necessary adjustments based on participant feedback.
 4. Increasing awareness and advocacy efforts within the community is crucial to reduce stigma and create more employment opportunities for former persons deprived of liberty, facilitating their successful reintegration into society.
-

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers declare that this study was conducted in strict compliance with ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, who were assured of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. The anonymity of the respondents was rigorously maintained to protect

their privacy, and their well-being was safeguarded throughout the research process. The researchers affirm that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of this study.

Additionally, the researchers strictly avoided plagiarism and ensured that there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings. The results of this study were used solely for research purposes, adhering to the highest standards of academic integrity.

Acknowledgments

The researchers extend profound gratitude to Burauen Community College, with special appreciation for its College Administrator, Dr. Jett C. Quebec, Atty. Absalon Apostol, and Ma'am Josefina Apostol, for their steadfast support. We also thank Dean Cheron Reyes of the College of Criminology for his invaluable assistance. Sir John Eric Go, Director of OSAS, merits our gratitude for approving our letters and providing moral support. Likewise, to Dr. Jessielyn Mesias-Aborod, College of Criminology Faculty of Visayas State University who served as the External Expert and making the paper more scholarly. Above all, we express deep appreciation to Burauen District Jail for granting approval and serving as the venue for our study, which greatly enriched our research paper.

REFERENCES

- Baffour, F. (2021). *Recidivism: Exploring Why Inmates Re-Offend in a Prison Facility in Ghana*.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348932454_Recidivism_Exploring_Why_Inmates_Re-Offend_in_a_Prison_Facility_in_Ghana
- Campbell, S., Greenwood, M., Prior, S., Shearer, T., Walkem, K., Young, S., Bywaters, D., & Walker, K. (2020). Purposive Sampling: Complex or Simple? Research Case Examples. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 25(8), 652–661. NCBI.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1744987120927206>
- Cano, J., Omega, Fr. G. R. L., & Omega, L. L. (2023). *THE LIFE IN JAIL: LIVED EXPERIENCES OF PERSONS DEPRIVED OF LIBERTY*.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369185587_THE_LIFE_IN_JAIL_LIVED_EXPERIENCES_OF_PERSONS_DEPRIVED_OF_LIBERTY
- Delong, C., & Reichert, J. (2019, January 9). *The victim-offender overlap: Examining the relationship between victimization and offending*. Icjia.illinois.gov.
<https://icjia.illinois.gov/researchhub/articles/the-victim-offender-overlap-examining-the-relationship-between-victimization-and-offending>
- Djoana, D., & Aoas, M. (2020). Effects of BJMP Livelihood Program to the Lives of Released Inmates. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 5(11). <https://ijisrt.com/assets/upload/files/IJISRT20NOV459.pdf>
- Education Reimagined. (2023, October 21). *Rethinking Infrastructure with Families at the Heart*. Education Reimagined. <https://education-reimagined.org/rethinking-infrastructure-with-families-at-the-heart/>
- Global Prison Trends. (2021). *A literature review Education in prison*.
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED615405.pdf>
- Inciardi, H. (2009). *The Effectiveness of Inmates Welfare and Development Program to the Preparedness for Re-Orientation in Society and Well-Being of Inmates of the Rizal Provincial Jail*. Issuu.
https://issuu.com/erica.fascinoitaliano/docs/rivista_2.pptx/s/93021

- Larsen , K. (2019). *Theories of Crime Causation | PDF | Criminology | Theory*. Scribd.
<https://www.scribd.com/document/452876712/THEORIES-OF-CRIME-CAUSATION-docx>
- Manka Nkimheng, Han, H.-R., Szanton, S. L., Alexander, K. A., Davey-Rothwell, M., Giger, J. T., Gitlin, L. N., Jin Hui Joo, Sokha Koeuth, Marx, K. A., Mingo, C. A., Samuel, L. J., Taylor, J. L., Wenzel, J., & Parisi, J. M. (2021). Exploring Challenges and Strategies in Partnering With Community-Based Organizations to Advance Intervention Development and Implementation With Older Adults. *the Gerontologist*, 62(8), 1104–1111.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/geront/gnab190>
- Ortaleza, L. R. B., & Nabe, N. (2020). *United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime*. PhD Research, Paper Publications, Paper Publication, Paper Publisher, Publication of Papers, Electrical Journal, Civil Journal, Medical Sciences Journal, Veterinary Sciences Journal, Healthcare Journal, Economics Journal.
<https://www.paperpublications.org/upload/book/A%20MULTIPLE%20CASE%20STUDY%20ON%20IN-PRISON-04012024-2.pdf>
- Reamico, C. (2022). Lived Experiences of Reintegration: A Case Study of How Former Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) Experienced Reintegration in a Local Context. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 7(5).
<https://ijisrt.com/assets/upload/files/IJISRT22MAY1251.pdf>
- Samilo, D., Ontong, J., Alba, C., & Guzman, D. D. (2020). Bureau of Jail Management and Penology Livelihood Program in Valenzuela City Jail. *Ascendens Asia Singapore – Bestlink College of the Philippines Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(1).
<https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/aasgbcjpmra/article/view/1436>
- Stahl, N., & King, J. (2020). Understanding and Using Trustworthiness in Qualitative Research. In *Journal of Developmental Education* (Vol. 44, Issue 1, pp. 26–28).
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1320570.pdf>
- Visher, C., Debus-Sherill, S., & Yahner, J. (2011). *Employment After Prison: A Longitudinal Study of Former Prisoners*.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233474673_Employment_After_Prison_A_Longitudinal_Study_of_Former_Prisoners
- Vivares, K. M. (2023). *The Reintegration of Ex-Convicts in Society: A Case Study*.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374933254_The_Reintegration_of_Ex-Convicts_in_Society_A_Case_Study
-